

Study of electrode kinetics and thermodynamic parameters of Metronidazole polarographically

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Abstract : The electrochemical reduction of antibacterial and antiprotozoal drug "Metronidazole" has been carried out in aqueous solution of different pH by direct current (DC) polarography. It exhibits two reduction peaks in acidic medium and one in basic medium. Along with different pH, studies of drug have been carried out with different concentrations of drug and at different temperatures. The reduction of MTZ was found to be irreversible so kinetic parameters (K_{f}^0 , αn) are evaluated using Meites-Israel and Gaur-Bhargava's methods. Thermodynamic parameters such as ΔH_p^\ddagger , ΔH_v^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger are also evaluated.

Keywords : Metronidazole, direct current polarography, kinetic parameters, thermodynamic parameters.

Introduction

Metronidazole (MTZ) [2-(2-methyl-5-nitroimidazol-1-yl)ethanol] is an antibacterial and antiprotozoal drug used to treat amebiasis; vaginitis; trichomonas infections; giardiasis; anaerobic bacteria; and treponemal infections. MTZ is also used for Treatment of Primary Episode of Clostridium difficile – Associated Diarrhea¹ and it is also clinically effective in reducing the incidence of post-operative infection in patients undergoing abdominal surgery². MTZ has molecular weight 171.154 g/mol and melting point 160 °C.

Metronidazole

[2-(2-Methyl-5-nitroimidazol-1-yl)ethanol]

Several methods have been reported for the determination of MTZ, including liquid chromatography³. Voltammetric methods have been applied to the study of the mechanism of nitroimidazoles as antimicrobial agents^{4,5} and its determination in pharmaceutical^{6,10} and clinical^{10,12} matrices. In present paper kinetic and thermodynamic

parameters of MTZ are calculated regarding to the different pH, different concentration of drug and different temperature. Kinetic parameters (K_{f}^0 , αn) are calculated by Meites-Israel¹³ and Gaur-Bhargava's methods¹⁴.

Experimental

Apparatus :

The digital DC polarograph (CL-357) of Elico Limited was used to record current-voltage data. This equipment has the three electrode assembly, dropping mercury electrode as working electrode, calomel as reference electrode and platinum electrode as counter electrode. Dropping mercury electrode had the characteristics $m = 2.422$ mg/s, $t = 2.5$ s and $h = 60$ cm.

The Elico digital pH meter model 111E was used to measure the pH of the analytes.

Reagents :

Metronidazole was obtained from Arbro Pharmaceuticals Limited, New Delhi, India.

Metronidazole was dissolved in 30% ethanol.

All solutions were prepared freshly with doubly distilled water and analytical reagent grade chemicals (Merck).

Proposed procedure :

The general procedure used to produce DC polarograms was as follows :

An aliquot (10 ml) of experimental solution which contains BR buffer (to maintain pH), Triton X-100 (Maxima suppresser) and water was placed in a dry, clean polarographic cell and deoxygenated with nitrogen for 15 min the current-voltage curves were measured manually.

The negative potential was applied to the working electrode with 150 mV/min scan rate and 100 nA/div sensitivity of current measurement. After the background polarogram had been obtained, aliquots of the required amounts of MTZ solution were added.

Results and discussion

The effect of pH on the current-voltage curve at a concentration $4.6 \times 10^{-3} M$ MTZ was studied over the pH range 2.3–12.3. MTZ gives rise to one or two reduction peaks depending on pH. In basic medium one reduction peak was obtained which refers to the six-electron reduction of nitro group to the corresponding amine. In acidic medium MTZ exhibits two reduction peaks. The height of the first wave is twice that of the second. The first wave corresponds to the reduction of the nitro group to form intermediate hydroxylamine, transferring four electrons while the second wave corresponds to the reduction of hydroxylamine to amine, transferring two electrons (4). The values of the diffusion current and half wave potential for the first wave are shown in Table 1. When we increase the pH of the solution from 2.3 to 12.3, i_d of the first wave decreases continuously; in acidic medium i_d of the second wave also decreases but in basic medium second wave collapses with the first wave.

Table 1. Effect of pH on diffusion current and half-wave potential of MTZ wave in BR buffer

Metronidazole = $4.6 \times 10^{-3} M$, Triton X-100 = 0.001%

pH	$E_{1/2}$ (V)	$i_d \times 100$ nA
2.3	-0.666	26.6
3.3	-0.773	25.5
4.3	-0.791	20.5
5.3	-0.847	17
6.3	-0.853	13.3
7.3	-0.837	10.6
8.3	-0.827	8.5
9.3	-0.825	7.9
10.3	-0.821	7.5
11.3	-0.813	7.6
12.3	-0.802	7.5

In acidic medium with increasing pH, the reduction process of nitro group becomes difficult so less no. of compounds reduces hence i_d decreases of both waves. But in basic medium nitro group reduces to amine without showing the presence of intermediate hydroxylamine, so both waves merged in a single wave.

Hence it shows MTZ gives two reduction waves in acidic medium and only one in basic medium. The half wave potentials ($E_{1/2}$) of the polarographic waves gets shifted towards more negative potential with an increase in pH from 2.3 to 6.3 (acidic medium) these results are supported by Zuman and co-workers^{15,17}, in basic medium $E_{1/2}$ decreases continuously from pH 7.3 to 12.3 these results are supported by Zuman¹⁸. The direct current polarogram (DCP) at different pH values for the reduction of MTZ at a concentration of $4.6 \times 10^{-3} M$ are shown in Fig. 1. These results show that in strong acidic medium the reduction of nitro group is easier, with increase in the pH, its reduction becomes difficult. Half wave potential $E_{1/2}$ is maximum at pH 6.3 (slightly acidic medium), the concentration of H^+ ion is very low so the reduction of nitro group is very difficult and in basic media, due to the availability of OH^- ions, reduction process occurs somewhat easier. So at pH 6.3, the reduction potential is highest.

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on MTZ polarogram : (a) at pH 3.3, (b) at pH 5.3 and (c) at pH 8.3.

The polarogram at pH 5.3 was much sharper and well defined so this pH was chosen for subsequent work. Further study is carried only for the first wave.

The effects of concentration of MTZ on polarogram are listed in Table 2, the concentration of MTZ was varied from $4.6 \times 10^{-4} M$ to $4.6 \times 10^{-3} M$. The plots of $\log [i/(i_d - i)]$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ were linear with slope values much

Table 2. Effect of concentration of MTZ on wave and hence on kinetic parameters in BR buffer at pH = 5.3, Triton X-100 = 0.001%

Conc. (M)	$E_{1/2}$ (V)	$i_d \times 100$ nA	D (cm ² s ⁻¹)	Slope (mV)	αn (M.I.) (V)	αn (G.B.) (V)	K_{fh}^0 (M.I.) (cm s ⁻¹)	K_{fh}^0 (G.B.) (cm s ⁻¹)
0.46×10^{-3}	-0.831	2.3	0.7101	0.1323	0.4096	0.4470	6.94×10^{-7}	2.79×10^{-7}
0.92×10^{-3}	-0.841	4.8	0.7732	0.1216	0.4457	0.4864	1.9×10^{-7}	6.77×10^{-8}
1.38×10^{-3}	-0.839	6.7	0.6695	0.1138	0.4762	0.5197	6.73×10^{-8}	2.2×10^{-8}
1.84×10^{-3}	-0.84	8.5	0.6061	0.1078	0.5027	0.5487	2.64×10^{-8}	7.98×10^{-9}
2.3×10^{-3}	-0.831	9.8	0.5156	0.1044	0.5191	0.5665	1.71×10^{-8}	5.01×10^{-9}
2.76×10^{-3}	-0.835	11	0.4511	0.1021	0.5308	0.5793	1.01×10^{-8}	2.84×10^{-9}
3.22×10^{-3}	-0.84	12.9	0.4558	0.1018	0.5324	0.5810	8.7×10^{-9}	2.41×10^{-9}
3.68×10^{-3}	-0.831	13.6	0.3879	0.1011	0.5361	0.5850	8.58×10^{-9}	2.4×10^{-9}
4.14×10^{-3}	-0.834	15.7	0.4084	0.1009	0.5371	0.5862	7.99×10^{-9}	2.22×10^{-9}
4.6×10^{-3}	-0.842	17	0.3879	0.0983	0.5513	0.6017	4.14×10^{-9}	1.08×10^{-9}

where, K_{fh}^0 (M.I.) = Formal rate constant obtained from Meites and Israel's method, K_{fh}^0 (G.B.) = Formal rate constant obtained from Gaur and Bhargava's method, D = Diffusion coefficient, αn = Transfer coefficient.

higher than expected for reversible reaction which suggest that electrode reaction is irreversible. The values of $E_{1/2}$ are almost constant and i_d increases with increasing concentration of MTZ as expected. Since the reduction of MTZ is irreversible hence kinetic parameters, like forward rate constant (K_{fh}^0) and transfer coefficient (αn) have been calculated using Meites-Israel and Gaur-Bhargava's methods :

Meites-Israel modification of Kotecky's method :

$$E_{d.e.} = E_{1/2} - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n} \log \frac{i}{(i_d - i)} \quad (1)$$

$$E_{1/2} = \frac{0.0591}{\alpha n} \log \frac{1.349 K_{fh}^0 t^{1/2}}{D^{1/2}} \quad (2)$$

Gaur-Bhargava modification :

$$E_{d.e.} = E_{1/2} - \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{i}{(i_d - i)} \quad (3)$$

$$E_{1/2} = \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{1.349 K_{fh}^0 t^{1/2}}{(\text{antilog } C) D^{1/2}} \quad (4)$$

where, K_{fh}^0 = formal rate constant for forward reaction, D = diffusion coefficient and αn = transfer coefficient. $-E_{d.e.}$ and $-E_{1/2}$ were determined with respect to calomel electrode. The values of αn were obtained by eq. (1) (Meites-Israel method) and eq. (3) (Gaur-Bhargava method). The values of K_{fh}^0 determined by eq. (2) (Meites-Israel method) and eq. (4) (Gaur-Bhargava method). The values of diffusion coefficient (D) were determined by

using Ilkovic equation.

$$(i_d)_{\max} = 706 n D^{1/2} C m^{2/3} t^{1/6} \quad (5)$$

all symbols have their usual meanings.

The effects of temperature on polarogram are listed in Table 3, at 30 °C well defined and well shaped wave was observed.

Further, thermodynamic parameter (ΔH_p^\ddagger , ΔH_v^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger) have been reported in Table 4. The enthalpy of activation at constant pressure (ΔH_p^\ddagger) has been calculated by substituting the value of slope of the plot ($\log K_{fh}^0$ vs $1/T$) in the Vant Hoff equation.

$$\Delta H_p^\ddagger = 2.303R \times \text{slope}$$

where R = gas constant.

The value of slope comes out to be 4.335×10^3 .

$$\Delta H_p^\ddagger = \Delta H_v^\ddagger + RT$$

From this relation ΔH_p^\ddagger (enthalpy change of activation at constant volume) was evaluated, the activation free energy change (ΔG^\ddagger) was determined by relationship.

$$K_{fh}^0 = (KT/h)r_o \exp(-\Delta G/RT)$$

where K = Boltzmann constant, h = Plank's constant, r_o = mean distance between depolarized ions in the bulk solution, R = gas constant, T = absolute temperature.

In general value of r_o is taken as 2×10^{-8} cm⁻¹. The entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) was calculated using following equation.

$$\Delta S^\ddagger = (\Delta H_v^\ddagger - \Delta G^\ddagger)/T$$

The plot of $\log K_{fh}^0$ vs $1/T$ is found to be linear from the

Table 3. Effect of temperature on Metronidazole wave and hence on kinetic parameters in BR buffer at pH 5.3
Metronidazole = 4.6×10^{-3} M, Triton X-100 = 0.001%

Temp. (°C)	$E_{1/2}$ (V)	$i_d \times 100$ nA	D ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	Slope (mV)	αn (M.I.) (V)	αn (G.B.) (V)	K_{th}^0 (M.I.) (cm s^{-1})	K_{th}^0 (G.B.) (cm s^{-1})
20	-0.835	7.3	0.44713	0.1037	0.5226	0.5703	1.31×10^{-8}	3.77×10^{-9}
25	-0.836	8	0.53699	0.0982	0.5515	0.6019	5.51×10^{-9}	1.45×10^{-9}
30	-0.838	8.3	0.57802	0.0961	0.5639	0.6154	3.65×10^{-9}	9.23×10^{-10}
35	-0.84	10.5	0.92506	0.0920	0.5889	0.6427	1.95×10^{-9}	4.56×10^{-10}
40	-0.842	11.7	1.14859	0.0903	0.5996	0.6544	1.46×10^{-9}	3.29×10^{-10}

slope of which the values of ΔH_p^\ddagger , ΔH_v^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger have been evaluated and presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Thermodynamic parameters at different temperatures

Temp. (°C)	ΔH_p^\ddagger (J/mol)	ΔH_v^\ddagger (J/mol)	ΔG^\ddagger (J/mol)	ΔS^\ddagger (J/Kelvin)
20	83.0×10^3	80.56×10^3	61.53×10^3	64.95
25	83.0×10^3	80.52×10^3	64.77×10^3	52.83
30	83.0×10^3	80.48×10^3	66.94×10^3	44.68
35	83.0×10^3	80.44×10^3	69.69×10^3	34.89
40	83.0×10^3	80.40×10^3	71.62×10^3	28.04

ΔH_p^\ddagger = Enthalpy change for activation process at constant pressure, ΔH_v^\ddagger = Enthalpy change for activation process at constant volume, ΔG^\ddagger = Gibbs free energy change for activation process, ΔS^\ddagger = Entropy change for activation process.

A perusal of the values of various quantities presents in Table 4 show that activation free energy change (ΔG^\ddagger) is positive at all the temperatures suggesting the non spontaneous nature of electrode process. Positive value of ΔS^\ddagger suggests that formation of activated state is accompanied by increase of entropy. From Table 4 it can be concluded that as we increase the temperature values of the ΔG^\ddagger increases and that of the ΔS^\ddagger decreases continuously, it shows that the non spontaneity of electrode process increases with temperature.

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